

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL STUDIES ON THE DAMAGE INITIATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES AT EXTREME TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of damage in the form of microcrack crack and interlaminar delamination within laminates under combined thermal and mechanical loadings. The material system investigated was a carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composite. The thermomechanical properties required for the analysis were obtained from tests on unidirectional laminates. Laminate investigated for damage initiation and growth is $[30/-30/90]_s$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$. Mechanical testing was conducted at 23 °C and -196°C. The microcrack and delamination were determined using acoustic emission and/or small incremental step loadings. The residual stresses due to difference in curing and test temperatures were calculated using classical laminated plate theory with thermo-mechanical properties generated, and their effect on the initiation of damage was assessed. The stress levels at the initiation of microcrack and delamination determined by experiment were compared with analytical predictions using maximum stress criteria. The interlaminar free-edge stresses were analyzed using a global-local model. The results of this stress analysis were compared with the experimental results. While the residual stresses increase with decreasing test temperature, so do the composite transverse and shear strengths, and these two effects compete in their influence on the stress to initial damages.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites are being explored for structural applications at extremely low temperatures, for example, in large cryogenic fuel tanks [1-3]. Exposure to these cryogenic temperatures can cause microcracks as well as delamination in the composites due to thermal residual stresses mainly brought on by the anisotropy in the composite ply coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Microcracks and delamination often result in a reduction in laminate stiffness and strength and changes in laminate CTE, and provides both a pathway for the ingress of moisture or corrosive chemicals and a possible pathway for loss of cryogenic fluids in the tanks.

The objective of this work was to develop a predictive capability for opening of the microcrack and free edge delamination in composite laminates subjected to mechanical loading at room temperature and cryogenic temperature. The material system investigated was a carbon fiber-reinforced toughened epoxy composite. The thermomechanical properties required for the analysis were obtained from tests on 8 ply unidirectional and $[\pm 45]_2S$ laminates. These laminates were tested at 23°C and -169°C using a custom-built cryogenic chamber installed on a mechanical test machine. Strain gage were used to measure the composite coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) continuously over the temperature range of 23°C to -196°C, and then immersed in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) to

record thermal strains at the corresponding temperatures. The details of this technique of CTE measurement using strain gages may be found elsewhere [4].

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system selected for this work was a graphite/toughened epoxy obtained in the form of unidirectional prepreg tape. Laminates, $[30/-30/90]_S$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ were fabricated according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The average fiber content was determined to be 65 percent by volume. The panel was cut into rectangular specimens, 15 cm long and 1.5 cm wide using a diamond-impregnated saw blade. Specimen edges were polished to enhance the microscopic image of damage. Unidirectional laminates were also fabricated to determine the necessary thermoelastic properties for calculation of the ply residual stresses and interlaminar stresses in the free-edge region and to measure the appropriate strengths required for the prediction of the onset of microcrack and delamination. The Poisson's ratio ν_{yz} was determined from the tensile loading of the $[90]_{24T}$ specimen with strains measured in the y- and z-directions and utilized to calculate G_{yz} . The strain in the z-direction was measured with a 0.79 mm long miniature strain gage mounted on the free-edge of the specimen.

An acoustic emission technique was employed to detect the onset of microcrack and delamination under incremental loading and unloading experiments. An acoustic emission transducer was mounted on the flat surface of the specimen using high-temperature vacuum grease to improve coupling between the specimen surface and transducer. At the first indication of ply crack, the specimen was unloaded and the ply crack was confirmed by microscopic examination of the specimen free edge. This procedure was repeated until indication of delamination. Figures 1a and 1b show a typical recording of the acoustic emission monitored as a function of applied load at room temperature. A sudden increase in the acoustic emission signal indicates the onset of microcrack and delamination. Figures 2a and 2b show optical micrographs of the 90-degree ply cracks and delamination at the specimen free edge. The exact location of the delamination with respect to the interfaces is also identified from these micrographs.

However, the use of acoustic emission was unsuccessful in certain cases at -196°C because of relatively high background noise due to boiling of the liquid nitrogen. The onset of microcrack and delamination was therefore determined by microscopic examination of the polished specimen free edges after a series of incremental loading and unloading experiments. In this procedure a specimen is loaded to a stress level slightly lower than that at which microcrack might be expected, then unloaded and the free edges examined in a microscope. If no crack is observed, the specimen is reloaded to a stress incrementally higher than before, unloaded, and examined again. This procedure is repeated until the ply crack and delamination were observed, which are usually accomplished in three to five iterations. The average value of the last two consecutive loads is then used to compute the stress required to initiate delamination. With this procedure, the error in the computed stress for ply crack and delamination is less than 5%.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Mechanical Properties and Residual Stress

Thermoelastic properties and strengths, which were experimentally determined at temperatures of interest. Table 1 shows the temperature dependent properties. Matrix dominant properties, transverse and shear properties and the CTE are dependent upon the temperatures. In Table 1, the script x refers to the fiber direction, and y and z refer to directions perpendicular to the fiber direction. The ν_{yz} was determined using $[90]_{16T}$ specimens by measuring strains in the y- and z-directions to calculate the

G_{yz} in conjunction with E_z . These properties were used to calculate the interlaminar stress distribution in the free-edge region to compare with the experimental results. The stress-free temperature was assumed to be equal to the cure temperature for the calculation of the residual curing stresses. The fiber volume is an average of five samples determined by the acid digestion method.

3.2 Onset of Microcrack

Acoustic emission is a very effective and accurate way to detect the onset of microcracking at 23°C, whereas it was found to be unsuccessful most of the time at -196°C, because of the presence of relatively high ambient noise mainly due to boiling of the liquid nitrogen. The onset of microcracking in such cases was determined by microscopic examination in conjunction with acoustic emission. In this procedure a specimen is loaded to a stress level slightly lower than that at which microcracking is expected, then unloaded and the free edges examined in a microscope. If no microcracks are observed, the specimen is reloaded to a stress incrementally higher than before, unloaded, and examined again. This procedure is repeated until the first crack is observed, which is usually accomplished in two to five iterations. Either the average value of the last two consecutive loads or the definitive acoustic emission signal, if present, is then taken as the stress for the onset of microcracking.

The residual stress in each ply within the laminate resulting from temperature difference between cure and test was calculated using the analytical model developed by Hahn and Pagano [5] in conjunction with the classical laminated plate theory. The transverse normal stress in the 90° ply was calculated using a commercially available code, ASCA [6], and compared with the experimentally determined $[90]_{8T}$ laminate strength at the corresponding temperatures.

Table 2 shows a comparison between experiment and analytical calculation in terms of transverse (90°) ply stress and strength. The total stress represents the stress calculated from the laminate stress (applied load) at the onset of microcracking and the curing residual stress in the 90° ply at the test temperature. The 90° curing residual stress increased with decreasing temperature and significantly influenced the microcracking in composite laminates.

The calculated total stresses in the 90° ply at the onset of microcracking are compared reasonably well with the corresponding measured transverse strength at both 23 and -196°C. A number of factors such as the constraining effect, ply thickness, inadequacy of the failure criteria, errors in the estimation of the residual stress, insufficient data, especially on transverse strengths, and the applied stress at the onset of microcracking, especially at -196°C, may contribute to the discrepancy between calculation and experiment. However, the approach taken in this work shows promise to predict the onset of microcracking at room temperature and cryogenic temperature.

3.3. Onset of Free Edge Delamination

Interlaminar stresses at each interface in the free-edge region were calculated using an analytical model [5,6]. Figures 3 and 4 show the distribution of interlaminar stresses, σ_z , τ_{xz} , and τ_{yz} at the midplane and the -30/90 interface under applied tensile stress of 100 Mpa alone. Figure 5 shows the interlaminar stresses under thermal loading due to curing residual stresses at 23°C and -196°C. The peak values present at the interior from the free edge rather than free edge under thermal loading. There is only an interlaminar normal tensile stress present at the midplane under either mechanical loading or thermal loading due to curing residual stresses. All three interlaminar stress components exist at the -30/90 interface. Interlaminar stresses at the 30/-30 interface were found to be insignificant compared to those at the midplane and the -30/90 interface.

The results of the interlaminar stress analyses are applied to the prediction of the onset of delamination at the free edge. The average value of each stress component at the free edge, instead of the maximum value, is assumed to be the effective stress level, i.e. that stress which is responsible for failure [7]. Average value was taken over a distance 0.127 mm (ply thickness) from the free edge. The delamination onset was assumed to occur when any of the effective stresses at each interface reached the corresponding uniaxial strength. The interlaminar stress components were calculated at the onset of delamination observed by experiment. Table 3 shows the results of the interlaminar stress components calculated at the indicated interfaces to compare with the corresponding strengths that were determined by experiment. The interlaminar tensile and shear strength were assumed to be identical to the transverse strength and in-plane strength, respectively. It is noted that the interlaminar shear stress component calculated was found to be insignificantly small compared to the shear strength. Thus, the interlaminar tensile stress at the midplane is the most critical stress component for the delamination on this laminate at both 23°C and -196°C and compared reasonably well with the corresponding strength. Delamination occurred at the midplane, between the 90° plies and/or the -30/90 interface, at which a higher interlaminar normal tensile stress is present. No delamination was observed at the 30/30 interface of the laminate in the early stages of delamination. A few transverse cracks were observed at 90° plies prior to delamination onset and appear to exert only a minimal influence on the stress level for the onset of delamination in this laminate. In this work, the variation of material properties as a function of temperature has been considered in analytical calculations in both residual stresses and interlaminar stresses.

4. SUMMARY

An investigation was conducted to observe the onset of delamination as a function of residual stress. Specimens of $[\pm 30/90]_S$ and $[0/45/-45/90]_S$ laminates were tested to determine the onset of microcrack and delamination under isolated or combined mechanical and thermal loads. Damage initiation was detected from acoustic emission and incremental loading and unloading experiments, and confirmed from microscopic examination of polished specimen edges. The both inplane ply stresses and interlaminar free-edge stresses were calculated using a global-local model [6]. The analytical results of stresses at the onset of microcrack and delamination compared reasonably well with the corresponding strengths that were experimentally determined. The material elastic properties as well as the ply transverse strength and interlaminar shear strength are significantly influenced by the cryogenic temperatures selected for this study. While the residual stresses increase with decreasing test temperature, so do the composite transverse and shear strengths, and these two effects compete in their influence on the stress to initial microcracking and delamination.

5. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Temperature dependent thermo-mechanical properties

	<u>23°C</u>	<u>-196°C</u>
Transverse modulus, E_y , Gpa	9.4	13.2
Shear modulus, $G_{xy}=G_{xz}$, Gpa	6.1	9.2
Transverse shear modulus, G_{yz} , Gpa	3.0	4.2
Transverse strength, Mpa	72	116
Coefficient of thermal expansion, $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$		
Longitudinal, α_x	-0.04	-0.2
Transverse, $\alpha_y=\alpha_z$	24.1	19.4

Table 2. Comparison of experiment with analytical calculation for 90° ply stress at the onset of microcracking

Laminate	Temp. °C	Applied stress at microcracking Mpa	Tensile stress in 90° ply, Mpa			90° ply strength Mpa
			Residual stress	Mechanical stress	Total stress	
[30/-30/90] _s	23	245	32	32	64	72
	-196	224	86	52	138	116
[0/45/-45/90] _s	23	340	32	48	80	72
	-196	276	86	51	137	116

Table 3. Comparison of experiment with analytical calculation for interlaminar normal stress at mid plane at the onset of delamination

Laminate	Temp. °C	Applied stress at delamination Mpa	Interlaminar normal stress at mid-plane, Mpa			90o ply strength Mpa
			residual	mechanical	total	
[30/-30/90] _s	23	307	11	55	66	72
	-196	332	27	68	95	116
[0/45/-45/90] _s	23	341	32	48	80	72
	-196	276	86	51	137	116

(a) Ply crack (1st loading)

(b) Delamination (2nd loading)

Figure 1. Acoustic emission event showing onset of ply crack and delamination for [30/-30/90]_s at room temperature

(a) Major delamination at midplane

(b) Delamination at -30/90 interface

Figure 2. Micrograph showing ply crack and delamination for [30/-30/90]_s at room temperature

Figure 3. Interlaminar stress at the mi-plane in the free edge region due to applied mechanical load

Figure 4. Interlaminar stresses at the -30/90 interface in the free edge region due to applied the load

(a) at 23 °C

(b) at -196 °C

Figure 5. Interlaminar normal stress distribution at the mid-plane due to residual stress